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Performance of Shanyou Wan 3. Loudi, Hunan Province, China. 1991.

Variety	Plant height (cm)	Panicle length (cm)	Spikelets/panicle (no.)	Seed set (%)	1,000-grain weight (g)	Maturity duration (d)	Grain yield (t/ha)	Grain yield over check (%)	Daily grain yield (kg/ha)	Daily grain yield over check (%)
Shanyou Wan 3	102.0	23.8	125.2	71.4	28.7	116.2	7.76***	14.85	66.75	8.01
Weiyou 64 (check)	86.3	21.9	98.8	72.3	29.8	109.2	6.75	-	61.8	-

*** = significant at 1% level by Duncan's SSR test.

weight is about 28 g. It matures in 115-120 d, about 7-8 d earlier than Weiyou 64, and is grown as a late-cropped rice in various areas. Shanyou Wan 3 has strong resistance to blast and sheath blight. It is tolerant of high temperatures in the early growth stages and of coldness in the late stages. Its milling recovery rate is about 75%, and its eating quality is acceptable.

The hybrid has wide adaptability, yielding well at elevations from 200 to

1,150 m above sea level and in different soils.

Seed production is high. The restorer line, Wan 3, has about a 10-d flowering duration, large panicles, many spikelets per unit area, and heavy pollen load. If the flowering synchronization is good between the parents, more than 3 t of hybrid seed/ha can generally be produced.

For spring seed production of Shanyou Wan 3 in Changsha, Hunan Province, the restorer line is generally seeded in late March. The seeding interval between the CMS line (Zhenshan 97 A) and the restorer line is 5.0-5.3 leaves on the main culm or 20-25 d. For autumn seed production, the restorer line is usually sown in mid-June, with an 11-13 d seeding interval for the CMS line. ■

Promising rice blast-resistant cultivars

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Rice blast is a serious disease in Coorg District of Karnataka, India. Resistance has been breaking down in some of the modern and local rice varieties, such as

Intan, BKB, PUB, Geerigesanna, and IET7191. We intensively screened rice germplasm for reaction to blast. Intan, which is grown on half of the rice area in the hill zone, was introduced in 1972 and lost its resistance to blast in 1983.

About 1,000 germplasm lines were screened for blast resistance under field conditions. Among the entries tested, NSN(H) 102-1988 was free from both leaf and neck blast during 1988 and 1992 kharif seasons. It also has desirable grain type, plant height, and duration and was selected for intensive screening with DWR4107 and Intan. These cultivars were screened in a

15-m² plot during 1990-92 kharif seasons. NSN(H) 102-1988 was free from both leaf and neck blast from 1990 to 1992.

Using the *Standard evaluation system for rice*, cultivar DWR4107 scored a maximum of 5 for both leaf and neck blast, and Intan scored a maximum of 5 for leaf blast and 9 for neck blast over the 5-yr study. NSN(H) 102-1988 was free from both leaf and neck blast disease and performed well in yield trials during 1990-92 kharif seasons. It had a mean yield of 2.7 t/ha compared with 2.5 t/ha for DWR4107 and 1.9 t/ha for Intan (see table). ■

Performance of NSN(H) 102-1988 at Ponnampet, S. Coorg, India. 1988-92.

Cultivar	Leaf blast ^a (score)					Neck blast ^a (score)					Yield (t/ha)			
	1988	1989	1990	1991	1992	1988	1989	1990	1991	1992	1990	1991	1992	Mean
NSN(H) 102-1988	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.6	4.0	1.9	2.7
DWR4107	3	-	-	0	5	5	-	-	0	5	2.2	4.3	0.8	2.5
Intan	7	9	5	5	5	5	-	5	9	9	1.6	3.3	0.8	1.9

^aScored using the *Standard evaluation system for rice*.

Integrated germplasm improvement—rainfed lowland

Luit, a short-duration rice variety for Assam, India

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Floods may occur anytime from May to early September in Assam, India. Farmers need a short-duration rice variety that yields well and can be harvested before (Feb-May) and after (mid-Sep to early Dec) the floodwaters. Rice farmers in the flood-affected areas until recently grew early-maturing varieties—Culture 1,

Heera, and traditional types—that are low-yielding, have undesirable plant type, and are affected by low temperature at flowering when grown after the flood. A hybridization program was initiated in 1988 to develop short-duration photoperiod-insensitive rice varieties with high yield. Luit (IET13622) was

developed by crossing Heera and Annada.

Luit has a growth duration of 95-100 d and may be grown both before and after the flood, either under wet direct seeding or transplanting. Luit is a semidwarf (91 cm), photoperiod-insensitive variety with well-exserted panicles. Grains are awnless and bold. The variety has a 1,000-grain weight of 26.1 g. Kernels are white, with nonglutinous endosperm and a trace of abdominal white. The milling recovery is 64.5%. Luit is moderately resistant to leaf blast and gall midge.

When transplanted during 1993 kharif (dry) season, Luit significantly outyielded check Heera in all four locations and significantly outyielded check Aditya in three of the four locations tested under the All India Coordinated Rice Improvement Project (AICRIP) (Table 1). Under wet seeding, Luit significantly outyielded Heera in nine out of 12 locations and Aditya in three out of 12 locations. Luit yielded a mean 5.0 t/ha under transplanting and 2.4 t/ha under wet seeding, ranking first and second in AICRIP trials, respectively.

The mean duration of Luit to 50% flowering was 80 d when transplanted and 71 d when wet seeded, which were 16-18 d more than Heera and 6-9 d more than Aditya (Table 1). The variety significantly outyielded Culture 1 (Table 2) in various locations in Assam under both conditions. The mean flowering duration under pre-flood situation was 69 d for both varieties. Under post-flood situation, Luit took 11 d longer than Culture 1 to attain 50% flowering. ■

Table 1. Yield performance of Luit under transplanting and wet seeding at various locations in the All India Coordinated Rice Improvement Project. 1993 kharif.

Location	Date sown	Date transplanted	Yield (t/ha)			LSD (0.05)
			Luit	Heera	Aditya	
<i>Transplanted</i>						
Coimbatore	9 Jun 93	9 Jul 93	4.1	3.5	3.9	0.3
Trichy	9 Jun 93	9 Jul 93	6.0	2.7	3.5	2.1
DRR, Hyderabad	2 Jul 93	2 Aug 93	6.2	2.3	4.2	1.0
Nawagaon	28 Jul 93	26 Aug 93	3.9	0.4	1.1	0.7
Mean			5.0	2.2	3.2	
Mean days to 50% flowering			80	64	74	
<i>Wet seeded</i>						
Mugad	22 Jun 93		6.0	2.7	3.0	1.5
Bankura	28 Jun 93		1.7	1.1	1.9	0.4
Hatwara	22 Jul 93		1.3	0.5	1.5	0.4
Karimganj	4 Sep 93		3.9	2.9	3.4	0.6
Titabar	15 Sep 93		1.7	2.5	1.3	0.4
Jabalpur	10 Jul 93		4.3	3.1	3.2	1.0
Rewa	17 Jul 93		1.9	1.0	1.7	0.6
Jadavpur	12 Jun 93		3.3	1.8	3.0	0.5
Ranchi	28 Jun 93		1.1	0.6	1.2	0.3
Raizabad	6 Jul 93		1.2	0.5	0.4	0.4
Banswara	1 Jul 93		1.3	1.3	2.1	0.4
IARI (New Delhi)	22 Jun 93		1.0	1.4	2.7	0.9
Mean			2.4	1.6	2.1	
Mean days to 50% flowering			71	53	62	

Table 2. Grain yield of Luit at various locations in Assam, India. 1991-93.

Location	Date sown	Date transplanted	Yield (t/ha)		Days to 50% flowering		LSD (0.05)
			Luit	Culture 1	Luit	Culture 1	
<i>Preflood</i>							
Titabar	25 Feb 91	-	4.5	2.8	68	65	0.5
Gerua	14 Mar 92	-	3.0	2.5	80	78	0.4
Mahakal	27 Mar 92	20 Apr 92	3.3	1.5	58	65	0.7
Mean	-	-	3.6	2.3	69	69	
<i>Postflood</i>							
Titabar	20 Aug 91	7 Sep 91	4.6	2.8	70	60	0.7
Titabar	9 Sep 91	-	3.5	2.4	62	52	0.9
Gerua	16 Aug 92	1 Sep 92	3.2	2.3	69	50	0.6
Karimganj	4 Sep 93	-	3.9	2.9	58	(Heera) 51	0.6
Karimganj	26 Aug 93	14 Sep 93	3.3	2.7	73	60	0.5
Mean	-	-	3.7	2.6	66	55	

Integrated germplasm improvement—upland

Centro Internacional de Agricultura Tropical's (CIAT's) upland rice germplasm development strategy

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CIAT began breeding upland rice for acid-soil savannas in 1984. The pro-

gram's main objective is to develop germplasm with a) tolerance for soil acidity, b) resistance to diseases (mainly leaf and panicle blast), c) resistance to insects (mainly *Tagosodes oryzae*), d) good grain quality (translucent, long and slender), and e) earliness (growth duration less than 115 d). The methodology used is shown in the figure.

Germplasm is exchanged yearly with the West Africa Rice Development Association (WARDA) and Centre de

Coopération Internationale en Recherche Agronomique pour le Développement (CIRAD-CA) in Africa, IRRRI in Asia, and national agricultural research systems (NARS) in Latin America.

North American materials were used in the early days as sources of grain quality.

These introduced lines are planted under acid soil conditions. The best lines are selected and organized in a potential parents nursery, which also has many